

Non-linear Electrical Conductivity of Carbon Nanotubes/WS₂ Nanotubes (Nanoparticles) Hybrid Films

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Electrical properties of carbon nanotubes films and composite materials consisting of carbon nanotubes and tungsten disulphide nanotubes (and fullerene-like nanoparticles) were investigated. Analysis of measured in temperature range 2–300 K temperature dependencies of the resistance $R(T)$ and IV -characteristics demonstrates that non-linear electrical conductivity of the films and composites is induced by contact barriers between conductive carbon nanotubes. Incorporation of semi-insulating WS₂ nanotubes (nanoparticles) leads to the increase of the samples' resistance due to decreasing of the number of current percolation paths between contacts. Experimental results of the measurements of DC-electrical properties are confirmed by the analysis of the frequency dependencies of the impedance of the samples in the range of 100 Hz – 1 MHz and dependencies of AC-conductivity on DC bias voltage.

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1. Introduction

Development of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) based composites is one of the most promising and advanced field of utilization of CNTs' extraordinary mechanical, electrical, optical and thermal properties for fabrication of functional and constructive materials, sensors and devices [1–3]. Due to high aspect ratio CNTs have advantages in comparison with many other fillers for reinforcement of mechanical properties, enhancement of electrical and thermal conductivity of composites, fabricating media with necessary transmission and absorption coefficients in different ranges of electromagnetic spectra. Different matrix materials are used for

CNTs-based composites fabrication, including various polymers [4–6], ceramics [7], and cements [8]. Recently, CNTs-based composites with glass microfiber matrix were fabricated and demonstrated higher electrical conductivity comparable with that of CNTs-based polymer composites [9]. In contrast to ordinary nanocomposites, in which the volume fraction of the CNTs is typically very low (less than a few percent), new class of composites (hybrids) are formed by both components (organic and inorganic) with similar volume fractions [10]. We fabricated earlier such new types of composites materials – hybrid films consisting of CNTs and inorganic WS₂ nanotubes (nanoparticles) [11, 12]. It should be noted that the method of fabrication of WS₂ nanotubes (WS₂-NT) and WS₂ nanoparticles (WS₂-NP) was developed soon after CNTs discovery demonstrating thus

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that low-dimensional cylindrical and spherical structures can be obtained not only from carbon but from inorganic materials as well [13]. Investigation of electrical properties of different types of CNT-based composites and hybrids is of high importance due to possibility of utilization them for a number of applications (for chemical, gas and biosensors, supercapacitors, photovoltaic devices etc.) both as active media and as electrode materials [10].

In this paper we focus our efforts on investigation of the influence of incorporation of inorganic tungsten disulphide nanotubes (nanoparticles) into CNTs films on electrical properties of hybrid films.

2. Experimental details

We used filtration process through cellulose acetate membrane filter (*Millipore*, 0.22 μm pore size) for fabrication of two different types of composite structures: SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films. Commercially available HipCO SWCNT (with diameter of 0.8–1.2 nm and length in the range of 100 nm–1 μm) and produced by CVD method MWCNT (with diameter of 30–50 nm and length in the range of 0.5 μm –200 μm) were utilized for the hybrid films fabrication. Inorganic WS₂ nanotubes (with diameter of majority of nanotubes of 20–180 nm and length in the range of 1–30 μm) were grown in the large-scale fluidized-bed reactor [14]. Inorganic fullerene-like WS₂ nanoparticles were synthesized by a high temperature (850 °C) reaction using H₂S gas and highly reducing conditions in a fluidized bed reactor. The typical fabrication procedure of hybrid films included the following steps: 1) preparation of suspensions of nanotubes (nanoparticles) – 0.2 mg of each type of nanotubes (SWCNT, MWCNT, and WS₂-NT and WS₂-NP) was dispersed into 1 wt% of SDS aqueous solution by ultrasonication for 1 h (ultrasonic frequency 44 kHz); 2) centrifugation of suspensions for 10 minutes at acceleration of 12000 *g*; 3) mixing of the suspensions in filtration cell in the ratio 50%:50% and filtration; 4) dissolving of the membrane filter in acetone

and transferring of the prepared films on the insulating polycrystalline Al₂O₃ substrates. Typical SEM image of SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid film is shown in Fig. 1. Samples of SWCNT, MWCNT and WS₂-NT were produced using the same filtration procedure for further comparative analysis of the electrical properties of hybrid films and CNTs films. Electrical contacts were made by Ag paint.

FIG. 1. SEM image of SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid film, scale bar is 200 nm.

The temperature dependencies of the resistance $R(T)$ and IV -characteristics of the samples were measured in the temperature range 2–300 K using He close-cycled refrigerator *Cryogenics Ltd*. Measurements of the frequency dependencies of the real and imaginary parts of the samples' impedance $Z'(f)$ and $Z''(f)$ as well as the dependencies of AC-conductivity on applied DC bias voltage $G(U_b)$ in the frequency range 100 Hz – 1 MHz and in the range of DC bias voltage 0–5 V were carried out using *LCR meter Agilent 4284A* at the temperatures 4.2 K, 77 K and 300 K. The amplitude of the sinusoidal signal was 40 mV. EIS Spectrum Analyser 1.0 program was used for modeling of the experimental results.

3. Experimental results and discussion

3.1. Temperature dependencies of the resistance

The temperature dependencies of the resistance $R(T)$ of SWCNT and MWCNT films, SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2. The temperature dependence of the resistance $R(T)$ (in log-log scale) of SWCNT and MWCNT films, SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films. Solid lines are the fitting results from the Eq. (1).

As one can see from Fig. 2 embedding of inorganic semi-insulating nanotubes (nanoparticles) into CNTs arrays induces increase of the resistance on more than 1 order of magnitude at $T = 300$ K. With the temperature decrease the difference between values of the resistance of SWCNT and SWCNT/WS₂-NT films as well as between values of the resistance of MWCNT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP films rises. It should be noted that $R(T)$ dependencies for all types of samples are characterized by negative temperature coefficient of the resistance ($dR/dT < 0$) and can be fitted in some intermediate temperature range within frame of fluctuation-induced tunnelling model proposed by Sheng [15] for disordered systems in which large in atomic scale highly conductive regions

are divided by small tunnel junctions:

$$R = R_0 \exp\left(\frac{T_1}{T + T_0}\right), \quad (1)$$

where

$$T_0 = \frac{16\varepsilon_0\hbar AV_0^{3/2}}{\pi e^2 k_B (2m_e)^{1/2} W^2}, \quad (2)$$

$$T_1 = \frac{8\varepsilon_0 AV_0^2}{e^2 k_B W}, \quad (3)$$

where ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity, \hbar is the Plank constant, A is the area of the tunnel junction, V_0 is the barrier height, e is the elementary charge, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, m_e is the electron effective mass, and W is the width of the tunnel junction.

Sheng's model is utilized for characterizing of conductivity of different types of disordered systems including CNTs-based polymer composites [5] and CNTs arrays of various morphology [16, 17]. In these cases, highly conductive parts of the systems are carbon nanotubes with metallic conductivity and tunnel junctions are the small intertube regions. Conductivity in these systems are limited by the number of tunnel junctions between CNTs. In the case when the thermal fluctuations energy $k_B T$ exceeds the average value of the contact barriers between carbon nanotubes with metallic properties in the high temperature range, the temperature dependencies of the resistance $R(T)$ with a positive coefficient of the resistance ($dR/dT > 0$) can be observed [18]. Deviation of the fitting curves from the experimental data in high temperature range can be explained by the rising influence of CNT with metallic conductivity due to increase of the tunneling probability. However permanent current paths with metallic conductivity were not formed due to large distance between electrodes (about several hundreds of μm) and therefore we did not observe a crossover to the $R(T)$ behavior with a positive coefficient of the resistance. It should be noted that the measurements of electrical properties of WS₂-NT hybrid films were impossible due to their very high resistance [12].

3.2. Current-voltage characteristics

Essential role of the contact barriers between conductive CNTs in films was confirmed by the results of the measurements of IV -characteristics. Non-linear IV -curves were observed both for CNTs films and hybrid films. As the temperature increases, the IV -curves have a tendency to more linear behavior. The IV -characteristics of SWCNT and MWCNT films, SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films measured at $T = 4$ K are shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3. The IV -characteristics of SWCNT and MWCNT films, SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films. The IV -characteristics in log-log scale are shown in the inset. Solid lines are the fitting results from the Eq. (4).

As one can see, IV -curves for all types of samples can be fitted within frame of Sheng's fluctuation-induced tunneling model according to the following formula proposed by Kaiser et al. [19]:

$$I = G_0 U \exp(U/U_0), \quad (4)$$

According Eq. (4) the conductance of the samples can be defined as:

$$G = G_0 \exp(U/U_0), \quad (5)$$

where G_0 is the temperature dependent low electric field conductance, U_0 is the voltage scale factor that gives an exponential increase in

conductance and depends strongly on the barrier energy.

As it has been mentioned above, at the temperature increasing the non-linearity of IV -curves becomes less significant. In Fig. 4 the set of the IV -curves for MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films measured in the whole temperature range 2–300 K is shown. Similar behavior (decreasing of non-linearity at the temperature rise) was observed for all types of the samples.

FIG. 4. The IV -characteristics of MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films, measured at $T = 4$ K. The part of the measured at $T = 4$ K IV -characteristics of MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films (in the range of currents 0–0.09 mA), are shown in the inset. Solid lines are the fitting results from the Eq. (4).

In order to estimate the IV -characteristics non-linearity coefficient we used the well-known formula defined as following [20]:

$$\alpha = \frac{dI}{dU} \cdot \frac{U}{I} = \frac{d \ln I}{d \ln U}. \quad (6)$$

We found that for all samples the values of the parameter α are comparable within the order of magnitude. For example, at $T = 4$ K and $U = 1$ V estimation according Eq. (6) gives the following results: $\alpha = 1.6 \pm 0.3$ for SWCNT films, $\alpha = 1.5 \pm 0.3$ for SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid films, $\alpha = 1.3 \pm 0.1$ for MWCNT films, $\alpha = 1.4 \pm 0.2$ for MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films.

Taking into account that $R(T)$ dependencies and non-linear IV -characteristics both for CNTs

films and for hybrid films can be approximated within the frame of fluctuation-induced tunneling model with the comparable values of non-linearity coefficient, we can assume that embedding of high resistive inorganic nanotubes (nanoparticles) induces increase of the resistance due to decrease of the number of current paths between electrodes. However similar non-linear properties of our samples are explained by the fact that main contribution to the resistance gives the most resistive contact barriers between conductive carbon nanotubes.

3.3. Impedance of hybrid films

As far as contact barriers between carbon nanotubes can provide not only resistive but also capacitive contribution to the impedance of the samples, we used impedance spectroscopy in order to determine and clarify their role in the electrical properties of CNTs films and hybrid films. As it was found earlier [11], 3 types of investigated samples (SWCNT and MWCNT films and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films) demonstrated properties inherent for the structures with prevailing active part of complex impedance in the entire investigated temperature interval 4.2–300 K and frequency range 100 Hz – 1 MHz. Moreover, positive value of the imaginary component of the impedance was observed for SWCNT and MWCNT films and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrids at $T = 4.2$ K as the DC bias voltage was applied due to rising role of kinetic inductance of individual carbon nanotubes [21].

Essential contribution of reactive (capacitive) part of the complex impedance to the conductivity was observed only for SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid films at temperature $T = 4.2$ K. The dependencies of the real and imaginary components of the impedance on frequency ($Z'(f)$ and $Z''(f)$) and results of the fitting of experimental data by equivalent circuits for this sample are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

The best fitting results were obtained for modeling using shown in the inset to Fig. 5 and to Fig. 6 equivalent circuit consisting of the following elements connected in series and in parallel:

FIG. 5. Frequency dependence of the real component of the impedance of SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid films measured at temperature $T = 4.2$ K and at different value of the applied DC voltage. Lines show the approximation of the experimental data by an equivalent circuit, presented in the inset.

FIG. 6. Frequency dependence of the imaginary component of the impedance of SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid films measured at temperature $T = 4.2$ K and at different value of the applied DC voltage. Lines show the approximation of the experimental data by an equivalent circuit, presented in the inset.

resistance R_1 , capacitance C , resistance R_2 and constant phase element CPE . We assume that the resistance R_1 and capacitance C simulates the average values of resistance and capacitance of the carbon nanotubes, resistance R_2 corresponds to the Ohmic resistance of the contact barriers

between the CNTs. The element *CPE* takes into account the variance in the values of the resistance and capacitance of the inter-tube contact barriers [22]. The admittance of the *CPE* is defined as:

$$Y_{CPE} = A_0(i\omega)^\alpha = A_0[\cos(\pi/2\alpha) + i\sin(\pi/2\alpha)], \quad (7)$$

where A_0 is the coefficient with the dimensionality depending on the value of α . In the case of $\alpha = 1$ the coefficient A_0 has the dimensionality of capacitance, while in the case $\alpha = 0$ the coefficient A_0 has the dimensionality of resistance. In the intermediate case dimensionality of A_0 can be considered as $\Omega^{-1}\text{s}^\alpha$ [23].

Existence of essential capacitive contribution at low temperatures to impedance of SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid films can be explained by large difference in sizes between conductive CNTs and non-conductive WS₂-NT (20–180 nm *vs* 0.8–1.2 nm in diameter and 1–30 μm *vs* 100 nm–1 μm in length, for WS₂-NT and SWCNT, respectively). From the another side, embedding of spherical WS₂-NT (with diameter in the of range 20–180 nm) into MWCNTs films (with diameter of 30–50 nm and length in the range of 0.5 nm–200 μm) does not induce essential capacitive contribution to impedance of hybrid films.

In order to clarify the nature of non-linearity of electrical properties of CNTs films and hybrid films, measurements of the dependencies of the real part of conductivity of our samples on DC bias voltage $G(U_b)$ were carried out. These dependencies for all types of the samples measured at frequencies $f = 100$ Hz and $f = 1$ MHz at $T = 4.2$ K are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

As it has been demonstrated in [24], the analysis of $G(U_b)$ dependencies of composite materials allows to separate contributions to non-linear properties from conductive matrix and non-conductive barriers. In the case of CNTs arrays in the low frequency range ($\omega\tau \ll 1$, where τ is a time constant of contacts barrier, ω is an angular frequency), non-linearity of $G(U_b)$ dependencies is induced by the contact barriers, in the low frequency range ($\omega\tau \gg 1$) – by carbon nanotubes.

FIG. 7. The dependencies of AC-conductivity of SWCNT and MWCNT films, SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films on DC bias voltage. Measurements are carried out at temperature $T = 4.2$ K and frequency $f = 100$ Hz.

FIG. 8. The dependencies of AC-conductivity of SWCNT and MWCNT films, SWCNT/WS₂-NT and MWCNT/WS₂-NP hybrid films on DC bias voltage. Measurements are carried out at temperature $T = 4.2$ K and frequency $f = 1$ MHz.

As one can see from Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, the rate of increase of the real part of impedance G with the rise of DC bias voltage (U_b) does not depend on frequency for all samples besides SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrid films. Therefore, we can conclude that for SWCNT/WS₂-NT hybrids the non-linearity is defined by contacts barriers in the

entire frequency range and for DC measurements as well. It should be noted, that highest measurement frequency 1 MHz fulfills to high frequency range criterion only for SWCNT/WS₂-NT samples due to low value of the reactive (capacitive) part of impedance in comparison with the active one in the frequency range of 100 Hz – 1 MHz for other samples. However, utilization of the same charge transport model for the description of room temperature frequency dependencies and *IV*-curves for all types of samples allow us to assume the main contribution from the contact barriers between CNTs to non-linear properties both for CNTs films and hybrid films.

4. Conclusions

AC and DC electrical properties of hybrid films consisting of CNTs and inorganic nanotubes (nanoparticles) WS₂ were investigated in the temperature range 2–300 K.

It was found that non-linear electrical conductivity of CNTs films and hybrid films consisting of CNTs and semi-insulating WS₂ nanotubes (nanoparticles) can be described within the frame of fluctuation-induced tunneling

model assuming that contact barriers between conductive CNTs give the main contribution to the resistance of the samples.

Embedding of semi-insulating tungsten disulphide nanotubes (nanoparticles) into arrays of SWCNT and MWCNT induces decrease of their conductivity due to destroying of the part of current percolation paths between electrodes.

Non-linear electrical properties of both types of samples (CNTs films and hybrid films) are defined by contact barriers between carbon nanotubes.

Influence of the ratio between carbon nanotubes and inorganic WS₂ nanotubes in hybrid films on their non-linear AC and DC conductivity will be described elsewhere.

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